

INFLUENCE OF THE DIAMOND-CERAMIC COMPOSITE THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY ON CUTTING PROPERTIES

L.Jaworska^{1*}, W. Zebala², P. Rutkowski³, P. Klimczyk¹, M.Rozmus¹

¹ Centre for Materials Research and Sintering Tech., Inst. of Advanced Manuf. Tech., Krakow 30-011, Poland, ² Faculty of Mech.Eng., Cracow University of Technology, Krakow, 31-864, Poland, ³ Dep. of Cer.&Refractories, Univ. of Sci. and Tech., Krakow 30-059, Poland

* Corresponding author (lucyna.jaworska@ios.krakow.pl)

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1 Introduction

Synthetic diamond can be made by the chemical vapour deposition (CVD) or high temperature and pressure synthesis (HP-HT). Submicrometer and micrometer diamond powders are mainly obtained from carbon precursors, during the HP-HT synthesis process (at about 5-6 GPa, 1670-1770 K). Large diamond crystals or polycrystals are used for cutting tool applications. Polycrystalline diamond, synthesized by means of the HP-HT method, is the most popular form of the diamond tool material and is generally known by its PCD acronym. These are obtained by sintering of diamond powders. The presence of a cobalt phase in diamond compacts has the effect of significant reduction of thermal resistance because cobalt is the catalyst of diamond to graphite and vice versa graphite to diamond transition process. Thermal stability of diamond material can be defined as its resistance to graphitization in an inert atmosphere at elevated temperatures. Also, the oxidation process occurs during heat treatment of diamond in oxygen at elevated temperatures. The oxidation of carbon (973 K and higher) proceeds, yielding gaseous products CO and/or CO₂. Graphitization and oxidation processes depend on size, purity and type of bonding phases for the polycrystalline diamond. One of the possibilities to increase thermal resistance of diamond materials with the bonding phase (PCD) is to reduce the popular cobalt content. Diamond compacts with cobalt are chemically stable only in the range 900 K- 1100 K, because of the graphitization process, while working temperatures may rise even higher. In such a situation, the development of new bonding phases in diamond composites is very much needed. Diamond content and diamond grain size distribution are carefully

controlled to provide the correct balance of wear resistance and toughness [1]. But mainly the thermal properties of cutting materials with another than cobalt bonding phase are changing. Ceramic materials exhibit differentiation of properties, such as thermal and electrical conductivities, hardness, abrasive wear resistance and corrosion resistance, resistance to temperature change and chemical inertness towards the workpiece material; all these characteristics influence the kind of machining [2]. All of these properties are also important for metal cutting process modeling.

The second group of commercial PCDs, for other applications, such as rock drills, are the materials with the Si bonding phase [3]. Because of the residual porosity these materials are not used for metalworking applications where the high quality of roughness is required. This paper presents results of the diamond composite with ceramic bonding phase thermal properties studies and analysis of possible material applications for material cutting.

2 Experimental

The mixtures containing 80 wt % diamond (3-6µm MDA, Element Six), 15 wt % of Ti-Si-C powder (47.1 vol % Ti₃SiC₂, TiSi₂, TiC and SiC manufactured using the SHS technique, AGH, Poland) and 5 wt % nanometric Ti(CN) (Neomat Co, Lithuania) powders were prepared. Before sintering, the powders were treated at 870 K for 30 min and at 0.8 Pa pressure. Next, they were sintered using a Bridgman-type high-pressure apparatus at 8.0±0.2 GPa and at the temperature of 2070±50 K. The samples were heated in an internal graphite heater with an inside diameter of 15 mm. The microstructure investigations were performed using the scanning (Jeol JSM-6460LV) microscope.

INFLUENCE OF THE DIAMOND-CERAMIC COMPOSITE THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY ON CUTTING PROPERTIES

The samples for microanalysis were prepared by lapping on a cast iron plate with diamond paste. Density was measured using the hydrostatic method. Hardness measurements were carried out with a Vickers apparatus at 9.8 N load. Young's modulus was measured using the ultrasonic method. Phase composition of the SHS powder and sintered bodies were identified by X-ray diffraction analysis, based on the ICDD database. XRD measurements were taken with an X'Pert Pro system (Panalytical) with monochromatic Cu K α 1 radiation. Heat measurements were performed on a Netzsch LFA 427 apparatus. Thermal diffusivity was determined by the laser pulse method (LFA). The test program was carried out in argon flow as referred to program measurements presented in Fig. 1. The laser voltage was 480V, pulse width 0.8 ms, flow rate of argon 150 ml/min. The diameter of samples was 10 mm, thickness about 4mm. If the value for thermal conductivity is unknown, it can be calculated from thermal diffusivity, density, and specific heat capacity of the material. To determine the specific heat, the laser pulse method was applied, using the Pyroceram 9606 and Inconel patterns with known coefficients of thermal expansion and specific heats. Specific heat of the diamond composite was calculated from the equation (1).

$$c_p^{samp.} = \frac{T_{\infty}^{ref}}{T_{\infty}^{sample}} \cdot \frac{Q^{samp.}}{Q^{ref}} \cdot \frac{V^{samp.}}{V^{ref}} \cdot \frac{\rho^{ref} \cdot D^{ref}}{\rho^{samp.} \cdot D^{samp.}} \cdot \frac{d_{orifice}^{2,samp.}}{d_{orifice}^{2,ref}} \cdot c_p^{ref} \quad (1)$$

where

- c_p specific heat of samples/ reference patterns, J/gK
- T samples/reference pattern temperature, K
- Q energy absorbed by the sample/reference pattern, J
- V amplitude of the signal gain of the sample/ref. pattern
- ρ apparent density, g/cm³
- D thickness of samples, mm
- d diameter of samples/ref. pattern measurement area, mm.

Simultaneous Thermogravimetric (TG) and Differential Thermal Analysis (DTA) measurements with the NETZSCH STA 449 F3 analyzer were carried out. The Al₂O₃ crucible was used, heating rate was 10K/min and maximal temperature was 1273 K. The measurements were carried out in argon (gas moisture 3 ppm/mol, presence of oxygen 2.00 ppm/mol and hydrocarbons 0.5 ppm/mol) and

in air. The Analyses were carried out using the Netzsch Proteus analysis program.

Fig. 1. Program of temperature change for thermal diffusivity measurements, performed with LFA 427 (Laser Flash Analysis).

The TNGA 160408 cutting insert has been prepared from diamond composite, Fig. 2.

Fig.2. TNGA 160408 cutting insert with a diamond cutting edge (black color).

Thermovision camera type Flir SC 620 with ThermoCAM Researcher software was used for temperature measurement during the dry cutting tests (turning) for the Ti6Al4V alloy workpiece. The following cutting parameters were applied: cutting speed $v_c = 30 - 200$ m/min, feed $f = 0.105$ mm and depth of cut $a_p = 0.5$ mm.

INFLUENCE OF THE DIAMOND-CERAMIC COMPOSITE THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY ON CUTTING PROPERTIES

3 Results and Discussion

The composite is formed of a skeleton-like diamond structure with pores filled with the bonding phase (Fig.3 a,b). The Ti_3SiC_2 decomposition process occurs during the sintering process. X-Ray analysis confirmed that the bonding has a multi-phase character, containing SiC, TiC, TiCN and $TiSi_2$ crystallites [4]. Selected physical and mechanical properties are presented in Table 1. The diamond composite material is characterized by very good mechanical properties and was applied successfully for tips of sliding burnishing tools where temperature of the tool work is not so high.

a)

b)

Fig. 3. Microstructures of diamond- Ti-Si-C composite. Grey particles are diamond a) b).

Table.1. Selected properties of diamond composite [5]

Composition wt%	Density* g/cm ³	Hardness** HV1	Young modulus, GPa
80 Diamond 15 Ti-Si-C 5 TiCN	3.5	5060±300	706

* Average measurement for three samples.

** Average of five hardness measurements, $\alpha = 0.05$.

The temperature in the cutting zone is one of the most important parameters affecting cutting performance. The temperature influences the possibility and suitability of the use of cutting speeds, feeds, depth of cut and also affects the tool life. It influences indirectly, but significantly productivity and economic efficiency of production. Heat balance is the form of energy balance and total heat in the cutting zone consists of heat in the workpiece, heat in the tool, heat in the chip and exhausted heat. The temperature of a chip is the highest because it consists of the heat from deformation. A smaller amount of heat is received by the tool (consisting of the part of heat from deformation and the part of heat from the friction between tool surface and the transitional area of workpiece) [6]. During the machining of titanium alloys, average temperature at the chip-tool interface was measured with the thermovision camera, Fig. 4 a,b. The maximal temperature at this area was about 900 K.

a)

b)

Fig.4. Thermograms of the cutting zone (the diamond composite edge and titanium alloy workpiece) for two cutting speeds: a) 30 m/min; b) 200 m/min

INFLUENCE OF THE DIAMOND-CERAMIC COMPOSITE THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY ON CUTTING PROPERTIES

During machining of the materials the majority of energy required to form the chips is converted into heat. A considerable amount of heat generated during machining is transferred into the cutting tool and workpiece [7]. The rate of heat transfer from the cutting zone is a very important parameter for machining. Increasing the heat in the cutting zone has a negative effect on the material of the tool tip. It may be negative, for example, for phase transformation processes (graphitization) or it may intensify the process of oxidation. Thermal diffusivity is a material property which describes the rate at which heat flows through the material, measured in mm^2/s or in mm^2/hr . In Fig. 5 the thermal diffusivity measurements of the diamond composite are presented.

Fig. 5. Thermal diffusivity of diamond – Ti-Si-C composite.

Thermal diffusivity is decreasing with the growth of temperature. The lowest value of thermal diffusivity $3 \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ for the diamond composite is for the range 870-970 K and it is the temperature of the cutting zone (for the titanium alloy machining). Thermal diffusivity of this material is about $7 \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ at room temperature. Because of low thermal diffusivity the heat is accumulated in the cutting zone for this diamond-ceramic composite. Good cutting properties depend on thermal resistance of the material or the use of lubricant-coolant process media. Cooling lubricants reduce a cutting temperature by 25 to 50% in the cutting zone. By decreasing the temperature, cooling lubricants enlarge the possible areas of diamond machining and eliminate in full or in part the effect of adhesion forces in tool contact areas, thus reducing both the

rate of the retarded layer formation and the force of chip friction on the diamond tool rake face [8]. The overwhelming part of cooling lubricants is of petroleum origin; renewable raw materials are hardly used. A considerable proportion of the lubricant is misted in the process and, on account of the heat generated in the cutting process, evaporates and is thus discharged into the ambient air. Due to their complex composition, cooling lubricants are classified as hazardous substances. Reducing environmental problems and the influence on workers by cooling lubricants require expensive investments in filtering and ventilation equipment at workplaces and cause high operating costs. One method, which has already been successfully used in practice, consists in minimum cooling lubrication (MCL) or rare dry cutting. For the investigated material the temperature in the cutting zone was measured in the dry cutting process. For the dry cutting process high thermal resistance materials are needed.

Thermal conductivity at 673 K for the investigated diamond composite is 156.5 W/mK . Natural diamond has a higher thermal conductivity than any other known material [9]. For synthetic diamond thermal conductivity is in the range 1000 W/mK . Thermal conductivity of the composites obtained from natural particulate diamond 10-14 μm in size was about 500 W/mK [6]. For the polycrystalline synthetic diamond containing up to 1.5% impurities and inclusions, 10-14 μm in size, thermal conductivity is about 190 W/mK [11]. Thermal conductivity at room temperature for commercial diamond compacts with the cobalt bonding phase up to 10 %vol. is in the range $150\text{-}600 \text{ W/mK}$ [8]. Thermal properties of the interface separating the diamond particles and properties of the bonding face are very significant for thermal conductivity of the diamond-ceramic composite [12]. Thermal conductivities of refractory metals and carbides are usually in the $7\text{-}170 \text{ W/mK}$. Thermal conductivity of SiC is in the range $40\text{-}145 \text{ W/mK}$, for TiC is 21 W/mK [13]. The presence of these ceramics decrease thermal conductivity of the diamond composite. A low value of thermal conductivity for the cutting edge, affects the presence of polycrystalline grain boundaries and also their incoherency. High thermal conductivity ensures rapid heat transfer from the cutting zone and thus it is less affected by the changes in the surface of the

INFLUENCE OF THE DIAMOND-CERAMIC COMPOSITE THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY ON CUTTING PROPERTIES

workpiece. Titanium carbides, titanium nitride-carbides and silicon carbides are included in the group of cutting materials. The bonding phase for the investigated diamond composite consists of SiC, TiC, TiCN and TiSi₂. For these materials the most important is the oxidation process in high temperatures. For example, the oxidation process of TiC begins at about 570 K and is finished at about 1070 K [14].

During diamond oxidation, two competitive processes occur; oxidation accompanied by surface graphitization [15]. The process of growth of diamond crystals requires the use of the catalyst material which is retained within the crystal after the synthesis process. The diamond micropowders therefore contain certain amounts of metallic catalyst materials which vary with the size of crystals. Thermal properties strongly depend on the type of diamond micropowders, their method of synthesis and used catalysts. The thermoanalytical study of diamond with the DTA-TG method are presented in Fig. 6. The analysis was carried out in argon.

Fig. 6. DTA-TG curves for MDA 36 diamond micropowder (E6)

It was noted that sharp exothermic peak appeared on the DTA curve during the heating process, which is assumed to result from oxidation and evaporation (which is the result of trace amounts of oxygen in the apparatus and argon as well as the release of moisture). Gaseous products CO and CO₂ are the results of diamond oxidation. The beginning of the peak is at 761 K and it is maximal at about 874 K. X-ray diffraction analysis detected that the diamond composite before thermoanalytical studies contains 1.7 % of graphite; after thermal studies in argon up

to 1270 K the graphite amount is about 3.7%. It is a low amount of graphite for PCD cutting tools, and the impact of this amount of graphite (after treating) on the cutting properties of cutting edge is negligible.

The thermoanalytical study of Ti-Si-C SHS powder with the DTA-TG method is presented in Fig. 7. The analysis also was carried out in argon. The exothermic peak appeared on the DTA curve during heating process at 841 K. The X-ray analysis of the Ti-Si-C SHS product shows the presence of 47.1 vol% of Ti₃SiC₂, TiSi₂, TiC and SiC. The exothermic peak for this material appears at about 670 K.

Due to the pseudo plastic behaviour of Ti₃SiC₂ ceramic (because of its specific layer structure), voids between diamond grains were well-filled by these ternary compounds, so for these systems there are secured thermodynamic conditions for the diamond, not graphite presence, especially for the first stage of the high pressure-high temperature sintering process [16]. But at the diamond sintering temperature there is the Ti₃SiC₂ decomposition process. Ti₃SiC₂ does not dissociate up to 2070 K, but it was found to be very susceptible to carburization and oxidation [17]. Ti₃SiC₂ dissociates into titanium carbide and silicon above 1570 K in argon atmosphere. The dissociation was accelerated when Ti₃SiC₂ was in contact with graphite (carbon)[18].

Fig.7. DTA-TG curves for Ti-Si-C powder consist of 47.1 vol% Ti₃SiC₂ and TiSi₂, TiC and SiC (SHS method, AGH, Poland)

In Figs 8 and 9 the DTA-TG curves for diamond and Ti₃SiC₂ powders but in air are shown.

INFLUENCE OF THE DIAMOND-CERAMIC COMPOSITE THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY ON CUTTING PROPERTIES

The exothermic peak appeared on the DTA curve during the heating process is assumed to result from diamond oxidation. The beginning of the peak is at 794 K and peak is maximal at about 874 K.

The oxidation process is visible for Ti-Si-C (SHS) powder beginning of the first exothermic peak appeared on the DTA curve at 653 K and the second peak appeared at 950 K. Peak temperatures for the studies in air and argon are very similar but in air the oxidation processes are most intensive, confirmed by the change in mass of samples.

The materials changing for experiments in air are extreme for about 843 K and it is the temperature of cutting zone for the titanium alloy turning at 200 m/min.

Fig. 8. DTA-TG curves for MDA 36 diamond micropowder (E6)

Fig.9. DTA-TG curves for Ti_3SiC_2 powder (AGH, Poland)

Numerical computation was carried out according to the finite element method [19].

Fig. 10. Numerical computation of temperature at the diamond composite cutting edge depends on thermal conductivity of the cutting material.

The computational simulation results presented in the first scheme (Fig.10) show the temperature of the cutting edge (the rake and the relief face), for the turning process using the following parameters: cutting speed $v_c = 30 - 200$ m/min, feed $f = 0.1$ mm/rev and depth of cut $a_p = 0.5$ mm, depend on the thermal conductivity of the cutting material. From this computational simulation it is known that temperature of the cutting zone is 870 K. Thermovision measurements indicated 896 K at the cutting zone for the same parameters of titanium alloy machining using the diamond composite edge (with thermal conductivity of 156 W/mK). For a hypothetical diamond monocrystal cutting edge with thermal conductivity of 1000 W/mK the temperature at the cutting edge will be about 500 K.

The second scheme (Fig. 11) was also prepared using computational simulations. It shows the temperature of the cutting zone for the same experiment depending on the cutting speed during the titanium alloy turning, using the diamond composite cutting edge. Two cutting speeds v_c were used: 100 m/min and 200 m/min. Temperatures at the cutting edge are 870 K and 750 K respectively. The lower value of the cutting speed influences the lower value of the cutting edge temperature. The machining process for the low cutting speed is not effective.

INFLUENCE OF THE DIAMOND-CERAMIC COMPOSITE THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY ON CUTTING PROPERTIES

Fig. 11. Numerical computation of temperature at the diamond composite cutting edge depends on cutting speed.

There are more parameters which influences the machining process and temperature at the cutting zone.

For example, the temperature of the cutting zone depends on the geometry of tools, machining parameters, cutting forces, friction between tool and workpiece material and thermal and mechanical properties of both workpiece and cutting materials. There is a compatibility between experimental temperature of cutting edge measurement and computational approaches. The temperature of the cutting edge work is in the range of the lowest value of the thermal diffusivity of the investigated diamond composite and at the range of the oxidation process for diamond MDA 36 (E6) and Ti-Si-C bonding phase. The graphite participation in the diamond composite after treatment up to 1270 K in argon is low. The intensive graphitization process for this material has not been observed.

Conclusions

The composite is formed of diamond particles surrounded by ceramic materials. This bonding phase improved the graphitization resistance at preserved atmospheres but has a significant influence on decreasing the thermal conductivity of the diamond composite to the 156.5 W/mK. Thermal properties depend strongly on the type of diamond micropowders, their method of synthesis and used catalysts.

The bonding phase for the investigated diamond composite consists of SiC, TiC, TiCN and TiSi₂. For these materials the high temperature oxidation process, which starts at about 670 K, is the most important.

The material with higher resistance for oxidation than carbides will be the most beneficial bonding phase for the diamond composite.

For this composite cutting edge the temperature at the cutting zone for the titanium alloy turning process at speed 200 m/min is 893 K. This material, because of low thermal diffusivity and tendency for oxidation, should work with the application of cooling lubricants.

There is a compatibility between experimental temperature of cutting edge measurement and computational approaches. Numerical computation based on the finite element method is a useful tool for the determination of temperature of cutting zone.

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INFLUENCE OF THE DIAMOND-CERAMIC COMPOSITE THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY ON CUTTING PROPERTIES

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